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INFLUENCE OF SOLVENTS ON SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF PRUCALOPRIDE SUCCINATE

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ABSTRACT

Prucalopride succinate is a selective 5-HT₄ receptor agonist. Two simple UV spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the estimation of Prucalopride succinate in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of prucalopride succinate in Acetate buffer (PH-5.0) and 0.1N NaoH was found to be 222nm and 228nm respectively and Beer-Lambert's law was obeyed over the concentration range 2- 16 μ g/ml. LOD and LOQ values of prucalopride succinate was found to be 0.143 μ g/ml, 0.472 μ g/ml and 0.112 μ g/ml, 0.369 μ g/ml in Acetate buffer and 0.1N NaoH respectively. The validation parameters were treated statistically with 't' test and significant differences were noted. The study clearly revealed that the solvents influence the determination of Prucalopride succinate. The methods described were rapid and easy can be applied for the estimation of Prucalopride succinate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

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INTRODUCTION

Prucalopride succinate is a class of dihydro-benzofuran-carboxamide. It causes stimulation of colonic mass movements which provide propulsion force for defecation. Prucalopride succinate, chemically 4-amino-5-chloro-N-[1-(3-methoxy propyl) piperidin-4yl]-2,3-dihydro-1-benzofuran-7-carboxamide, butanedioic acid. The molecular formula of Prucalopride succinate is $C_{22}H_{32}ClN_3O_7$ and its molecular weight is 485.96 g/mol. Choice of solvent can shift peaks to shorter or longer λ depends on their nature of the interaction of the particular solvent with the environment of the chromophore in the excited state of the molecule. Solvents can affect the fine structure of absorption curves as well as the intensities and wavelengths of maxima. There are various methods available for the estimation of Prucalopride succinate. Among these methods High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), spectrophotometric methods and LC/MS reported for the quantification of Prucalopride succinate. The effect of solvents for the estimation of Prucalopride succinate has not been reported. In the present study two simple UV spectrophotometric methods were developed for estimation of Prucalopride succinate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations among these the sensitive one can be confirmed by calculating limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification as per ICH guidelines.

Fig.No.1: Chemical Structure of Prucalopride Succinate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Absorbance measurements were made on double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer with spectral band width of 0.5nm and wavelength accuracy of ± 0.3 nm with 10 mm matched quartz cuvettes (ELICO SL 244) were employed. Prucalopride succinate reference standard was gifted by SUN Pharma Ltd, Guwahati. Sodium hydroxide, Sodium acetate and Acetic acid used was of analytical grade purchased from National scientific Laboratories Vijayawada. Methanol –Govt supply.

PREPARATION OF STANDARD STOCK SOLUTIONS OF PRUCALOPRIDE SUCCINATE

50mg of Prucalopride succinate pharmaceutical grade was accurately weighed two times separately and transferred into two different 50ml volumetric flasks and dissolved in Methanol, volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent the stock solution obtained was 1000ppm(1mg/ml).

DETERMINATION OF λ_{max}

The two different stock solutions were suitably diluted with Acetate buffer and 0.1N NaoH to get a concentration of 10 ppm(10 μ g/ml) and scanned in the UV region ranges from 200nm-400nm. The wave length at which maximum absorbance observed was noted. The absorbance of the standard solutions containing the Acetate buffer and 0.1N NaoH observed at 222nm and 228nm respectively.

BEER'S LAMBERT LAW

The two different stock solutions were suitably diluted to get concentration range from 2-16 μ g/ml and their absorbance were measured at λ_{max} 222nm and 228 nm. Calibration curve constructed for Prucalopride succinate in two different solvents by taking concentration (μ g/ml) on x-axis and absorbance on y-axis.

THE PROPOSED METHODS ARE VALIDATED FOR THE FOLLOWING PARAMETERS

Linearity

Linearity range of the proposed UV methods were find out. In order to find out the linearity range of proposed UV methods a curve was constructed by plotting absorbance obtained for the analyte against its concentrations in Acetate buffer and 0.1N NaoH. A series of 2(μ g/ml), 4(μ g/ml), 6(μ g/ml), 8(μ g/ml), 10(μ g/ml), 12(μ g/ml), 14(μ g/ml) and 16(μ g/ml) were prepared for standard calibration curve and absorbances were observed. The results were subjected to regression analysis by the least squares method to calculate slope(m), intercept(c) and regression coefficient (R^2).

Precision

Precision of method was determined in terms of repeatability (with in run precision), intermediate precision and reproducibility (between run precision).

Repeatability

Repeatability of the method was determined by analyzing three samples of 4($\mu\text{g/ml}$), 8($\mu\text{g/ml}$), 12($\mu\text{g/ml}$) concentration in two different solvents and the %RSD and SE were calculated.

Intermediate precision:**Intraday precision:**

It was calculated by analyzing six test samples of Prucalopride succinate on the same day. Intraday precision of the method was determined by evaluating the samples of Prucalopride succinate on different days or and on two different spectrophotometers in the same laboratory.

Reproducibility:

The sample solutions were prepared and analyzed in different labs.

Sensitivity:

The sensitivity of the proposed UV method was measured in terms of limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD and LOQ were calculated using formula:

$$\text{LOD}=3.3 \sigma/s \text{ \& LOQ}=10 \sigma/s$$

Where σ = standard deviation of Y-intercepts of regression lines.

S= slope of the calibration curve.

Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorption coefficient:

It is calculated by using the following formula

$$S = \epsilon \cdot p$$

Where S= sandell's sensitivity

ϵ = specific extinction coefficient

P = concentration of substance in mg/liter.

Robustness:

To determine the robustness of the method, the experimental conditions were altered and assay was evaluated. Sample solutions were prepared and absorbances were observed at $\pm 5\text{nm}$ from absorption maxima.

Accuracy:

Accuracy of the methods were confirmed by studying recovery at three different concentrations for 80, 100, 120% of these expected, in accordance with ICH guidelines by replicate analysis. Standard drug solutions were added to a pre analyzed sample solution and %drug content was measured.

ANALYSIS OF TABLET FORMULATIONS

Twenty tablets were weighed and grinded, amount of the tablet powder equivalent to 25mg of Prucalopride succinate was taken, extracted with methanol and dilutions were made with respective solvents. Analyze these solutions by using proposed UV methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The wavelength maxima obtained for Prucalopride succinate in two different solvents were 222nm, 228nm in Acetate buffer and 0.1N NaoH respectively. (Fig.Nos.4&5). The developed UV spectrophotometric methods followed beer's law in the range of 2-16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Fig.Nos.2&3). The relative standard deviation values were observed less than '1' indicates precision of the method, the lower standard error value indicates the accuracy of the method. The molar extinction coefficient, sandell's sensitivity, and LOD & LOQ values were calculated as per ICH guide lines, the values are depicted in table no.5. Based on LOD and LOQ values, the solvents were ranked 0.1N NaoH > Actate buffer. The study clearly revealed the sensitivity of the method improved in the presence of 0.1N NaoH than in Actate buffer. 0.1N NaoH was found to be more sensitive as it offered lowest LOD and LOQ values. LOD and LOQ values are subjected to statistically and data shown in Table.no:3&4. Significant differences were observed between the solvents used for the determination of drug. Lowest LOD and LOQ values were observed with the solvent i.e 0.1N NaoH.

The LOD and LOQ values of Prucalopride succinate in Acetate buffer and 0.1N NaoH were subjected to t-test. The calculated 't value compared with t- table value, the observed value was greater than the table value indicated that the significant differences between the LOD and LOQ values of Prucalopride succinate in two different solvents.

CONCLUSION

The proposed methods were easy to perform and applicable for estimation of Prucalopride succinate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations in Quality control laboratories.

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Table No.1: Linearity of Prucalopride succinate in Acetate buffer.

S.No.	Concentration(ppm)	Absorbance
1.	2	0.138
2.	4	0.244
3.	6	0.386
4.	8	0.488
5.	10	0.61
6.	12	0.732
7.	14	0.854
8.	16	0.976

Fig.No.2: Calibration curve of Prucalopride succinate in Acetate buffer

Table.No. 2: Linearity of Prucalopride succinate in 0.1N NaoH.

S.No.	Concentration(ppm)	Absorbance
1.	2	0.142
2.	4	0.266
3.	6	0.374
4.	8	0.512
5.	10	0.64
6.	12	0.768
7.	14	0.896
8.	16	1.021

Fig.No.3: Calibration curve of Prucalopride succinate in 0.1N NaOH.

Fig.No.4: λmax of Prucalopride succinate in Acetate buffer.

Fig.No.5: λmax of Prucalopride succinate in 0.1N NaOH

Table No.3: Limit of Detection (LOD).

S.No	0.1N NaoH LOD± S.D(n=6)	Acetate buffer LOD ± S.D(n=6)	t _{Cal}	t _{Tab}	D.F
1.	0.0112±8X10 ⁻⁴	0.0143±10.35X10 ⁻⁴	5.02	2.228	10

D.F = Degrees of freedom , t_{Cal} - Calculated t value, t_{Tab} - t table value

Table .No.4: Limit of Quantification (LOQ).

S.No	0.1N NaoH LOQ±S.D(n=6)	Acetatebuffer LOQ±S.D(n=6)	t _{Cal}	t _{Tab}	D.F
1.	0.0369±8.02X10 ⁻⁴	0.0472±7.26X10 ⁻⁴	23.6	2.228	10

D.F = Degrees of freedom , t_{Cal} - Calculated t value, t_{Tab} - t table value

Table.No.5: Validation Parameters of Proposed UV methods.

S.no	Parameters	Acetate buffer	0.1N NaoH
1.	λ _{max}	222	228
2.	Range	2-16 µg/ml	2-16 µg/ml
3.	Regression equation	Y=0.060x+0.0137	Y=0.0632x+0.088
4.	Slope	0.060	0.0632
5.	Intercept	0.0137	0.088
6.	A ^{1%} _{1cm}	624.1	649.5
7.	R ²	0.9995	0.9996
8.	Molar absorption coefficient (litre/mole.cm ⁻¹)	3.033 X 10 ⁴	3.1565 X 10 ⁴
9.	LOD	0.0143 µg/ml	0.0112 µg/ml
10.	LOQ	0.0472 µg/ml	0.0369 µg/ml
11.	Sandell's sensitivity (µg/cm ² /0.001absorbance unit)	0.0166	0.0157

Table.No. 6: Analysis of Tablets by Proposed methods.

S.No.	Tablet Brand Name	Labelled Amount(mg)	% Recovery ± S.D(n=3)		SE	
			Acetate Buffer	0.1N NaoH	Acetate Buffer	0.1N NaoH
1	Pruvict2	2	99.36 ± 0.03	99.96±0.02	0.017	0.011
2	Pruease2	2	99.62 ± 0.036	99.91±0.0173	0.021	0.009
3	Prumax	2	99.82 ± 0.04	99.98±0.01	0.023	0.0057

S.D: Standard Deviation, SE: Standard error

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